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Research Article

**PERCEPTION OF PEOPLE TOWARDS BLOOD DONATION
ITS BENEFITS AND HARMS**¹Dr. Saher Maqbool Kayani, ²Adeela Shafiq, ³Dr. Rabia Basray¹Polyclinic Hospital, Islamabad, ²THQ Kamoki, ³Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences, Islamabad.**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Blood donation is very safe medical procedure nowadays. Donated blood is lifesaving for individuals who need it. In Pakistan the concept of Voluntary unpaid blood donation (VUBD) almost does not exist due to insufficient knowledge, false perception and awareness regarding blood donation. (Dhara and Dinesh, 2012)

Objectives: The main objective of this study was to determine the public perception towards blood donation i.e. Its benefits and harms among population of Bahawalpur.

Methods: A Cross sectional study was designed in general population of Bahawalpur from January 2018 to March 2018. A total of 350 respondents were interviewed with the help of self-created and well- structured questionnaire. Data analysis was performed by using (SPSS version 21) for windows. Descriptive statistics was used as analysis plan. A scoring of 1 and 0 was done for right and wrong response respectively.

Results: The majority of participants (52.9%) were non donors among which (28%) were females. Among the donor group majority (37.71%) were males. 88.3% respondents were aware of blood donation. Among the donor's major reason for donating blood was noble cause in 69.4%.

Conclusion: In Pakistan there is a very less percentage of women among blood donors. The reasons for this are number of factors which include beliefs that bothers on religious and cultural and challenges associated with donor education. Awareness session and strategies should be held for decreasing the perception that the blood donation is not harmful can lead to an increase in blood donation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Human blood is one of the most precious life-saving component. Blood transfusion has been considered as one of the most important process in medical science and responsible for saving millions of lives around the world. The quantity and quality of available for transfusion is still at its crucial stage worldwide, especially in the developing countries.

According to World Health Organization pop, the need of blood in South East Asia is approximate 15.6 million, but collection is 9.4 million units annually, leaving a gigantic gap of 6 million units. In Indian, all 2760 registered blood bank over 1.2 billion populations are suitable to collect 9 million units of blood annually but they collect only 7 million units per year. However, these blood banks are organized and promoted by government, private organizations and other semi government affiliations, but promoting blood donation and spreading awareness among the people, remains the major problem. **(Ahmed et al., 2014)**

Consistently, individuals around the globe of all ages need blood transfusions to survive. Internationally, roughly 108 million units of blood are given every year. Half of these are gathered in the high-wage nations with blood gift rate of 36.8 gifts for each 1,000 though rate is just 3.6 gifts for each 1,000 in low-wage nations like Pakistan. The components in charge of low blood accumulation in Pakistan incorporate absence of training and mindfulness about the need of safe blood in the group and significance of deliberate unpaid blood gift (VUBD) and high commonness of Hepatitis B, C, HIV/AIDS and sickness. **(Mullah, 2013)**

Blood has constantly held hidden appeal for all and is thought to be the living power of our body. In current time, blood has been utilized subsequent to 1930 for different purposes. After the presentation of blood donation centers it turns out to be all the more generally utilized as a part of patients. In Pakistan more than 1.5 million pints of blood are gathered every year. Among them around 65% is from substitution givers, 25% from volunteer givers and around 10% from expert benefactors. **(Mullah, 2013)**

In the current scenario, more and more emphasis is towards voluntary donation and maintain the transfusion transmitted infections negative benefactor by World Health Organization and National Aids Control Society.^{3,4} The flattering towards blood donation is mainly due to inadequate and incorrect information for its necessity and misconceptions related to fears of physical harm in the process of

donating blood. The sagacity toward voluntary blood donation could be influenced to a large extent by socio-demographic variables of information among the common population.⁵ One of the important point motivating people for benefactor of blood is their interaction with medical staff. Traditionally the hospital staff including the non-medical and paramedical staff (support staff) is looked upon by the community as a cradle of information and encouragement for various health related matters including blood donation. Also the non-medical staffs are intricate in significant interaction with the patients and their caretakers, in some instances more than physicians themselves. **(Salaudeen and Odeh, 2011)**

Since contagious diseases can be pass through blood transfusion, there is need to cradle blood from a low threat population. The first expedient towards blood safety is to buck up volunteers and regular blood donors who will donate blood at least three times a year. The civil policy on blood advocates that blood donation should be exclusively voluntary and that donors should not be ill.^[3] Little wonder many nations across the world are continually estimating their blood donor system in the light of the current demand for blood and its products and in some cases, the reduction of the available eligible donors due to the stringent criteria in place to ensure blood safety. **(Salaudeen and Odeh, 2011)**

Today in the progressive world, most blood donors are unpaid benefactors who donate blood for a local supply. In underdeveloped countries, substantiate supplies are of finite number and donors usually give blood when family or friends need a transfusion (directed donation). Many blood donors donate as an act of noble deed like charity, but in countries that allow paid donation some donors are paid, and in some cases there are provocation other than money such as paid off time from work. Donors can also have drawn blood for their own future use. Donating is relatively safe, but some donors have swallowing where the needle is inserted or may feel faint. **(Salaudeen and Odeh, 2011)**

Now days, the utilization of entire blood is a very much acknowledged and generally utilized measure without which numerous present day surgical techniques couldn't be done. Given blood can be lifesaving for people who have lost a lot of blood in light of genuine mishaps, common and military clashes, broad tragedies or surgery, and also, for people who have turned out to be seriously pallid or have perilously low platelet tallies due to certain hematological illnesses, for example, sickle cell

pallor or medications, for example, disease treatment. Subsequently, blood is an essential worry to the general public. (Thaver et al., 2014)

Though safe blood transfusion services amend in the country, but exertion are still required in certain areas to improve blood banks and improve recruitment of willingly donors. 4 Different studies supervise in Pakistan demonstrate that adolescent population have relatively lower prevalence of Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, and HIV. It was also found that juvenile people donate the least blood⁶ and as level of education increases, the proportion of blood donors decreases.(Thaver et al., 2014)

Since young students are considered the safest group of blood donors⁸, they need to be utilized as a source of safe and no recompense donations. However, there is an insufficiency of data about awareness regarding blood affiliated issues including its donation. It would be important to understand information gaps and no generalization in this population so that appropriate people awareness scheme can be mark accordingly and school children are ready to become coming blood donors once they reach a blood donating age.(Thaver et al., 2014)

Objectives:

The main objective of this study was to determine the public perception towards blood donation i.e. Its knowledge, benefits and harms among population of Bahawalpur.

Aim of study:

This study is mainly aimed to assess the awareness of blood donation and to gather basic information from donors/non donors and acknowledged their estimation towards blood donation its benefits and harms, and to suggest measures to increase the awareness and motivation towards blood donation. Therefore, the objective of this study was to determine the knowledge, benefits and harms about blood donation among population of Bahawalpur.

Chapter 2

Literature Review:

Blood gift and transfusion are surprisingly sheltered medicinal methods. In any case, states of mind, convictions and level of learning connected with blood gift and transfusion may influence such methods. Consequently, the point of this study was to decide the state of mind, conviction and information about blood gift and transfusion in Saudi Population. The present study was led in the Department of Physiology, College of Medicine, King Saud University Hospitals, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. A very

much organized Arabic poll was utilized to assess the state of mind, conviction and information with respect to blood gift and transfusion. The example comprised of 335 males (55%) and 274 females (45%); most of the specimen (65.84%) were non-givers. These non-contributors (78.98%) were between the ages of 15-30 years. The 88.5% of the general population who took an interest in the study trusted that blood gift was not hurtful, 20% of them expressed that they would deny blood transfusion regardless of the fact that they were in need in light of the danger of obtaining irresistible illness. 84.5% favored direct gift, (49%) of the specimen expressed that they would acknowledge blood gift just from relatives, 55.1% trusted that blood transfusion was protected. In any case, 11.6% guaranteed to have procured irresistible illness after blood transfusion, 58% female not withstanding 11.34% male liked to get blood from female benefactor and 69.5% did not know whether the blood donation centers needed blood or not and 17.4% trusted that every single surgical method require blood transfusion. Different fears, question in doctor's facility and absence of data may serve as a vital issue to be tended to when creating givers enlistment projects or battles to clear misguided judgments about blood gift. Likewise, open ought to realize that various screening measures are executed to guarantee that blood gift is ok for the giver and that transfusion of the gave blood is alright for the beneficiary. Catchphrases: Attitude, Beliefs, Level of Knowledge, Blood Donation and Transfusion.(Al-Drees, 2008)

Blood gift is a noteworthy worry to the general public as gave blood is lifesaving for people who need it. In Pakistan, the idea of intentional blood contributors is just about non-existent because of the nonattendance of blood benefactor inspiration and maintenance procedures. The solid, dynamic and responsive enormous understudy populace can be potential blood benefactor to meet the protected blood necessities. The target of this study was to decide the learning, mentality and practices about blood gift among undergrad medicinal understudies in Karachi. A cross sectional study was directed in two open and one private therapeutic school in Karachi from January to March 2012. A sum of 600 restorative understudies were met with the assistance of organized survey. Information examination was performed in SPSS rendition 19. Numerous relapses were utilized to look at the impact of various free variables on a solitary ward variable to test the measurable noteworthiness at 95% certainty level. The lion's share of members (92%) had fitting information with respect to the different parts of blood gift. Disposition space demonstrated that

around 42% of understudies were sure about blood gift. Around half of understudies demonstrated readiness to give blood. Subsequent to changing for potential confounders, male sexual orientation was connected with fitting information, inspirational state of mind and eagerness for blood gift when looked at against female sex. Good information about blood gift practices is not changing in giving blood. Intelligent mindfulness sessions on blood gift ought to be sorted out amid undergrad years and open doors for blood gift ought to be made for the understudies, which can incredibly improve the development for "willful non-compensated blood gift", to guarantee great nature of blood and safe cutting edge medicinal consideration. **(Ahmed et al., 2014)**

Blood gift is by all accounts a basic component which warrants genuine consideration inside different groups. The study surveyed the learning, convictions, recognitions and encounters in regards to intentional non-compensated blood gifts among the adolescent and grown-ups in Walvis Bay and Swakopmund (beach front towns), Windhoek (capital city) and Oshakati and Ongwediva (northern rustic towns). The fundamental reason for the study was to recognize procedures and components that impact enlistment and maintenance of intentional non-compensated blood benefactors in Namibia with the perspective to enhancing blood gift rehearses. An explorative, quantitative, subjective strategy was utilized to get data from the young and grown-ups in the individual locales as specified previously. The general population, wellbeing specialists and researchers/understudies shape the example. Meetings were led in English and translation done where fundamental. At least 100 individuals for each site were focused from people in general, ± 50 wellbeing experts from each of the four towns and 14 wellbeing staff (both center and research center wellbeing laborers) at the Blood Transfusion Services of Namibia. Albeit 71.4% of the Namibian Blood Transfusion Service work force demonstrated that the givers get data and advising while the staying 28.6% expressed the inverse. When all is said in done the mission of giving the MOHSS safe blood for over 40 years is being figured it out. However, the changing environment and progression of the rising illnesses of the previous decade's guides for modification methodologies to enrolled and hold contributors, create focused on correspondence behavioral data, persistent in-administration preparing in most recent advances and fiery government funded instruction. **(Haoses-Gorases and Katjire, 2013)**

One of the greatest difficulties to blood wellbeing especially in Sub-Saharan Africa is getting to

sheltered and satisfactory amounts of blood and blood items. The present study was intended to explore the level of female sexual orientation interest in the blood gift process in Sokoto, North Western Nigeria. This is a review study, which was completed in UsmanuDanfodiyo University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto, Nigeria. Materials and strategies: In this present review study, we explored the level of female sex interest in the blood gift process by assessing the blood gift records of 14,956 blood contributors who went by the blood donation center in UsmanuDanfodiyo University showing healing facility for blood gift reason somewhere around 2010 and 2013 in Sokoto, North Western Nigeria. Subjects for this review study included 14,965 blood contributors. Mean age and age scope of blood givers was 27.1 ± 8.18 and 18-50 years individually. The aggregate number of blood contributors from January 2010 to July 2013 was 14,965. Contributors included 14,871 guys (99.4%) and 94 females (0.64%). The quantity of male contributors was fundamentally higher than that of female givers ($P=0.0001$). The appropriation of male and female benefactors yearly from 2010 to 2013 was (2,916, 4,787, 4687, 2,481) and (25, 28, 16 and 25) separately. Of the aggregate number of blood contributors, a huge 14,891 (99.5%) were family substitution benefactors while 74 (0.50%) were willful non-compensated blood givers (0.0001). Out of the 74 deliberate non-compensated benefactors, 18 were females while 56 were guys. There was a male sex predisposition in the likelihood of a benefactor being intentional no remunerated. Of the female contributors, 18/94 (19.1%) were deliberately non-compensated contrasted with 56/14,871 (0.38%) $P=0.003$. Female sex interest in the blood gift in North Western Nigeria is fundamentally lower contrasted with discoveries from created nations. There is have to create proof based instructive, social and religious-centered intercession that urges females to give blood. There is have to instruct the female populace to address the negative discernments against blood gift and the significance of blood gift. **(Erhabor et al., 2014)**

The Scottish National Blood Transfusion administration have built up an instructive project went for guaranteeing an exclusive expectation of administer to blood transfusions to minimize danger to patients and social insurance Specialists, this paper examines whether learning and comprehension of, and states of mind towards, safe practice declined after some time taking after fulfillment of module 1 of the project. An online study was controlled to a scope of medicinal services experts who had finished the module. The study apparatus tried information and discovered perspectives on blood transfusion

practice and view of the module's significance. Correlations were made between members 6e8 weeks, 12e14 months and 22e24 months since module fruition. Inside and out meetings were directed with a sub-test of study respondents to investigate demeanors in more detail. Discoveries show confirmation of a slight however measurably critical diminishment in the level of accentuation respondents set on the significance of comprehension parts of transfusions as time slipped by, however no distinction was found in learning between the individuals who took the course all the more as of late and the individuals who were up to two years' post-module. The study's discoveries show that acknowledgment of the significance of safe practice decays after some time and consequently additionally proposes that continuous refresher courses are critical to keep up safe practice. **(Sreedhar Krishna, 2008)**

The minimal scholastic writing on open mentalities towards blood gift in our nation specifies the most critical explanation behind not giving blood identified with the individual impression of the blood transfusion. We meant to consider the consciousness of blood gift and view of benefactors/non-givers towards gift. Higher the salary, rate of non-givers was high i.e. 48%. Larger part i.e. 98% individuals knew about blood gift; fundamentally through coordinators (55%) trailed by the universities (20%), schools (5%). Among non-givers (38%) trepidation of disease (21%), apprehension of needle (15%) was seen, however 62% needed to be contributors, inactivity was the main consideration (46%) for the non-gift of blood. Sixty-eight for every penny (of individuals (n=200) knew about dangers in blood transfusion. Significant purpose behind giving blood was benefactor card as an impetus in 87%, honorable motivation in 60%. There is have to convey mindfulness and to energize people in the group to begin and afterward keep giving blood. **(S. and B., 2015)**

The non-restorative staff are included in extensive connection with the patients and their overseers, in some occasions more than doctors themselves. They are looked upon by the group as a wellspring of learning and inspiration for different wellbeing related matters. The impact of states of mind, standards and impression of bolster staff on group inspiration different issues including blood gift is not generally concentrated on. Goal to discover the observation and perspectives of this gathering of healing center staff about blood gift are additionally rare. Strategies A volunteer gathering of 23 non-therapeutic healing facility staff were examined utilizing the 'Free posting' method. Of these 7 most

expressive members were chosen for 'Heap Sorting' exercise. Information was dissected utilizing Visual Anthropic, adaptation 1.0 programming. Consequence of 119 reactions recorded, 15 commonest reactions were utilized for heap sorting exercise. These then sorted into 5 bunches in view of the impression of the respondents. The respondents could recognize the areas with their point of view. Dominant part of the respondents trusted that blood gift was for the most part considered as a respectable and life sparing act. It was watched that there were a few confusions in regards to blood gift. The gathering likewise consented to these confusions. Conclusion Such activities help us to comprehend the distinctive parts of a subject (blood gift) as saw by the objective gathering. Such a comprehension is imperative to plan any instruction program for the gathering. Such studies help in giving the premise to more illustrative quantitative studies. **(Dhara and Dinesh, 2012)**

On the off chance that blood gathering offices are to keep taking care of the demand for a protected and sufficient blood supply, correspondence experts must discover approaches to select more givers to give blood more times. One conceivable demographic to target is youngsters, who could supply blood for a considerable length of time to come on the off chance that they got to be standard givers. Past examination shows that the individuals who have not gave before report that they will probably give on the off chance that they feel compelled to hold fast to society's endorsed social standards. Then again, givers refer to that they are propelled by philanthropy to help those in need. The aftereffects of this 2 x 2 factorial examination, which connected both of these inspirations to print ads, demonstrated that benefactors and non-givers alike appraised charitable advertisements higher than social standards promotions on the general state of mind evaluation scale. Additionally, both gatherings reported that they will probably give blood after presentation to charitable advertisements. Proceeded with exploration is expected to decide compelling specialized apparatuses that can achieve the full scope of individuals important keep the country's blood supply pumping. **(Windley, 2006)**

Blood accumulation organizations face significant issues in getting enough blood contributors, especially since the appearance of HIV and worries about disease. The present paper plots the testing of a proposed model of blood gift conduct that was tried on a specimen of individuals in Perth, Western Australia. The outcomes recommend that there are danger issues that should be tended to however, then again, there are sparks that can be utilized to build

blood benefactors from the present to a great degree low five for every penny of the populace. **(Aldamiz-echevarria and Aguirre-Garcia., 2014)**

Blood transfusion is a standard treatment for weakness in both inpatients and outpatients. In any case, few studies on the treatment have analyzed the patient's point of view. This concentrate along these lines looked to distinguish how well patients comprehend the part of blood transfusion in their treatment and whether it causes them inconvenience. All therapeutically stable grown-ups who had gotten a blood transfusion at an Ohio healing facility over a five-week period in 2009 were recognized; a comfort test of 21 of those patients took an interest in semi structured interviews enduring 15 to 30 minutes. The analysts recorded and deciphered the meetings and performed a topical examination. Four subjects rose: paternalism and basic leadership, patients' learning, blood wellbeing and organization, and the medical attendant's part. Members said that on the grounds that a doctor chose the transfusion would occur, they didn't comprehend that there were different choices for treating their paleness; pretransfusion composed materials weren't satisfactory to clarify dangers and advantages of the system; they had worries about the security of the blood supply; and they esteemed medical attendants' feelings. These subjective discoveries recommend that clinicians might miss chances to enhance patients' learning of and solace with blood transfusion and that they can better address patients' issues some time recently, amid, and after the strategy. Further research is justified. **(TO, 2011)**

The procedure of blood transfusion has picked up validity since ahead of schedule, and frequently, deadly tries different things with liquids. This anticipate talks about how transfusion advanced inside the principal half of the twentieth century from an apparent "encumbrance" to a significant asset. As war has punctuated this period, wartime need is regularly misjudged as the sole boost for therapeutic advancement. Existing records depict military solution as being described by radical wartime leaps forward, punctuated by times of relative stasis amid peacetime. Rather, this paper proposes that military pharmaceutical essentially reflects regular citizen hone, but with an alternate chain of command of needs. This exposition will demonstrate that war did not animate mechanical development, but rather only required the usage of existing innovations, infrequently at a test stage. Drawing on minutes of wartime gatherings and contemporary therapeutic diaries, this exposition contends that war arrangements combined a sorted out benefactor board

and enhanced the logistics of blood transport however did not straightforwardly enhance clinical drug. Besides, this paper investigates how incremental advancement in wartime can be halfway ascribed to the changed stream of data. **(Sreedhar Krishna, 2008)**

An overview of 1735 blood focuses (131) and healing facilities (1604) in the US demonstrated that blood gathering rate per thousand US populace of give age somewhere around 18 and 65a long time diminished from 85.6 (aggregate number of accumulations,13,890) in 2004 contrasted with 88.0 (aggregate number of accumulations,14,259) in 2001 (2.7 % diminish). As blood use increments with the coming of more unpredictable helpful mediations, blood gathering focuses are discovering it hard to keep up a sufficient blood stock in light of the fact that the accessibility of blood for transfusion is subject to volunteer givers. In the US around 40% of the grown-up populace is qualified to give blood, yet only 5% around 5% do as such . In addition, just 3.5% of the age-qualified populace gives blood in Australia. Gift tension because of a past blood gift experience may be a real indicator of a contributor's future aim not to give blood. Giving simple access to gift locales, overcoming time requests, (for example, booking appointments for gift hours) and feeling sure for the methodology, more adaptable gift hours, and expanding the quantity of locales where gift occur have decidedly affected blood gift aims. The present study expected to decide blood givers' view of the blood gift experience, behavioral and full of feeling mentalities toward gift, and demographic qualities that may impact their goal to give blood later on. A self-controlled poll was utilized to gather information on the level of instruction, level of learning about blood gift, full of feeling, and mental segments on blood gift choice passionate status, evaluations of the physical state of the blood gift focus, treatment of benefactors by the staff who give the specialized also, managerial oversight of blood gift, also, the sufficiency of information's gave in the blood. **(Bağışi and Sonuçları, 2012)**

To evaluate the learning, state of mind and practice about blood security and gift. Cross sectional explanatory study. Spot of Study: Lahore Medical and Dental College. A shut finished survey comprising of inquiries to assess the learning with respect to blood security and gift, disposition and view of the medicinal understudies was appropriately filled by 142 understudies of First year MBBS. The information were entered and broke down utilizing Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) programming rendition 20. Out of 142 students 77.5%

expected to give blood in future, however just 66.9% had ever given blood and out of which, 18.3% of givers were newbies. Learning on blood security and gift was altogether connected with blood gift status. Very little of the therapeutic understudies under study had sufficient learning on blood wellbeing and gift and the principle reason they gave for low gift was that individuals have dread in giving blood. **(MIRZA et al.)**

Blood gift is the main method for securing blood to meet crisis necessities in instances of street auto collisions, intricacies of pregnancy and labor, different iron deficient issue and surgical crises among others. Internationally, 80 million units of blood are given every year, except just two million units are given in sub-Saharan Africa where the need is gigantic. The goal of this study was to decide the conduct of the understudies of a tertiary establishment in Nigeria towards deliberate blood gift. This is an elucidating cross-sectional study, which included understudies of a tertiary foundation in Nigeria. A multistage inspecting system was utilized in selecting the members for this study. A semi-organized self-managed poll was utilized to gather data on socio-demographic attributes, learning, demeanor and variables influencing willful blood gift. The information got were dissected utilizing EPI-INFO 2005 programming Version 3.3.2. Less than 66% (61%) of aggregate respondents had great learning of blood gift. More than seventy-five percent (85%) of the respondents had never given blood. Of the 15% that had given, just 3% gave deliberately. Among those that had ever given, guys (57%) were more than females. A significant number of the contributors gave for relatives (57%). Most of the respondents were constrained to give on account of crisis circumstances (75%). The reasons why numerous did not give were absence of chance (45%) because of tight address plan and deficient information (24%). Blessing things, for example, hematonic, T-shirts and wrist groups (29%) would propel respondents to give. The Students' Union body and different Organizations in the University ought to incorporate a blood gift drive in their month to month/yearly exercises. The University powers, the University wellbeing administration focus and the Hematology Department of the Teaching healing facility ought to team up in advancing willful blood gift among the understudies. **(Salaudeen and Odeh, 2011)**

The lack of blood in blood donation centers in Saudi Arabia is fundamentally because of the expansion in requests as an aftereffect of an increment in the populace size and the expanded number of complex

treatments, for example, chemotherapy, organ transplants and heart surgeries, which require a lot of blood and blood items. Destinations. The present study meant to survey the learning, mentality, and to comprehend the obstructions confronting blood gift among restorative understudies. In a cross-sectional, distinct study 408 therapeutic understudies were evaluated without anyone else controlled survey led at Taibah University, College of Medicine, Madinah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia between April 2015 and June 2015. Members were chosen by helpful non-irregular inspecting procedure. The study populace comprised of 408 respondents. Most of the respondents (71.8%) had never given blood. Wellbeing reasons were the most well-known reason for declining to give blood 17.6%. While nothing stresses a large portion of the guys (47.8%) with respect to blood gift, sickness transmission positioned first among females (28.3%). Most of the members (87.7%) trust that there was no enough attention to give blood in the general public. Conclusion. Expanding the consciousness of blood gift in the general public particularly among those in the therapeutic field may build the quantity of givers in Saudi Arabia. Moreover, the implantation of some motivational variables may be useful. **(Al-Rahili et al., 2015)**

The King Khalid University Hospital (KKUH) Blood Bank suffers frequent shortages of blood components because it depends partly on involuntary blood donors, and is expending considerable effort to increase its pool of voluntary donors. The present study aimed to investigate the attitude of King Saud University (KSU) students towards blood donation to determine the factors that would increase voluntary blood donations at KKUH. A cross-sectional study was conducted at 6 colleges (n = 600) in KSU, Riyadh, between February and March 2012 using a self-administered questionnaire distributed to donors (n = 300) and non-donors (n = 300). All respondents were male. Ninety-eight percent of KSU students agreed that blood donation is important; 92% of non-donors believed that blood bank centers are in need of voluntary blood donations. Seventy-six percent of non-donors were opposed to importing blood, reflecting their opinion that blood should be available locally. The majority of the students did not consider fear or donation venue strong discouraging factors against blood donation and objected to monetary compensation, but would accept a token or gift. The present survey highlighted the need to invest in awareness and motivational campaigns on blood donation among university students so that current donors will continue donating and non-donors will be encouraged to begin donating. Addressing the issues

raised by the non-donors will pave the way to their becoming regular blood donors. This will eventually facilitate the establishment of a blood donor system based on voluntary, non-remunerated donations. **(Al-Faris et al., 2013)**

Undergrads frame an expansive and critical gathering of populace qualified for blood gift. Ponders report that understudies don't give much, and therapeutic understudies' blood gift rate is less when contrasted with non-restorative understudies. To survey and analyze the information, state of mind, and routine of blood gift among medicinal and non-restorative Nepalese understudies. A cross-sectional distinct study utilizing organized self-regulated poll was directed in understudies of restorative (MBBS) and non-medicinal projects of various schools of Nepal. Complete 456 understudies, 177 non-medicinal and 279 therapeutic, partook; 28.5% understudies were contributors. More restorative understudies gave blood, all the more regularly, and were more educated in all parts of blood and blood gift related information (p values 0.01 or less). In both gatherings, proportionately more young men gave than young ladies. Basic explanations behind not giving incorporated no solicitation, medicinally unfit, no data about blood accumulation administrations, apprehension of shortcoming, and dread identified with vein puncture. Moral fulfillment was the commonest motivation to give. Among Nepalese understudies, medicinal understudies give more and are more learned than non-therapeutic understudies. Absence of data and absence of direct demands are critical reasons for less givers in the non-therapeutic gathering and young ladies. **(Mamatya et al., 2012)**

Blood is central to sparing lives and is thought to be the power that supports our bodies. To survey the states of mind and practices of wellbeing science understudies with respect to blood gift. A cross-sectional study was utilized to survey the states of mind and practices of wellbeing science understudies with respect to blood gift. 453 understudies (56.7% male) from the four wellbeing resources (Pharmacy, Genetic designing, Nursing, and Hospital organization) were studied between May to July, 2013. Implies, rates, dispersion and standard deviation were measured. Besides, a t-test was connected to assess the change among the methods. Male understudies demonstrated more uplifting state of mind scores in regards to blood gift (Mean, 3.91) than female understudies (Mean, 3.87). Only 66.0% had tried their blood bunch and a minority (11.3%) had given blood amid their life. Besides, a couple of them (3.9%) experienced distress subsequent to giving blood, and the dominant part of them gave

blood deliberately (60.8%). The results of the ebb and flow research uncovered that the states of mind and practices of the wellbeing science understudies concerning blood gift should have been improved. Helpful correspondence between medicinal services experts and givers ought to be made strides. **(Batiha and ALBashtawy, 2016).**

The theme of the 2012 World Blood Donor Day campaign, "Every blood donor is a hero" focuses on the idea that every one of us can become a hero by giving blood. Today, Blood Transfusion Services constitute a crucial part of any healthcare delivery system. Adequate and safe supply of blood and blood components is essential, to enable a wide range of critical care procedures to be carried out in hospitals. The objective of the present study was to identify the level of knowledge of blood donation among voluntary blood donors attending blood bank of Krishna Hospital Karad and to correlate the knowledge with socio demographic variables. 100 voluntary Blood donors between the ages of 18 and 55 years were selected by Non probability Convenient Sampling technique. Descriptive Survey Design was employed for study. Structured knowledge questionnaire was given to assess their knowledge on Blood Donation. The study sample consisted of 64 males (64%) and 36 females (36%). The overall knowledge on blood donation among respondents was observed as good 10%, average 56%, and poor 34%. In males the overall knowledge level was found good among 9%, average 52% and poor 39%. In females, good knowledge level was observed among 14%, average 49%, and poor 37%. Education and gender was significantly associated with knowledge of blood donation whereas education religion blood group and age were not statistically significant. In the present study researcher concluded that there is need for health education regarding blood donation, which will ultimately increase the awareness among general population to motivate for voluntary blood donation. **(Pranjali P. Sharma, 2013)**

Blood is the most given tissue in medicinal practice and a veritable instrument in life-sparing circumstances. In spite of broad endeavors around the world, the accessibility of blood still stays short. In India there is a need of around 8 million units of blood for each year and stand out third are acquired from deliberate givers. This study was attempted to check the familiarity with blood gift among the relatives of patients going to our wards. It was led among 57 members on the premise of a poll. 74% members thought about Blood gift yet just 21% had given blood. General mindfulness about blood gift

was high. Members did not know particular insights about the subject. There was an inspirational state of mind to blood gift. Already predominant myths are no more noteworthy. Despite a positive mentality towards blood gift, endeavors still should be attempted to advance further towards a definitive objective of killing deficiency of blood. **(Pranjali P. Sharma, 2013)**

There are not very many studies showing the mindfulness level of our general public about "blood prerequisite" and "blood gift". The point of the present study was to examine practices and demeanors towards blood gift among understudies from Kars Health High School. The study was directed in Kars Health High School amongst March and May 2009. In the present study, was utilized a questionnaire taking into account the writing survey and that intended to evaluate socio demographic attributes (18 things) and practices and dispositions towards blood gift (34 things). 291 understudies took an interest in this study. The got information were assessed utilizing distinct investigation. It is watched that the understudies (12.0%) deliberate give blood at a rate much over the Turkish normal (1.5%), an incredible dominant part of the members consider giving blood (61.5%) and a large portion of them have uplifting states of mind and practices toward blood gift. A lion's share of understudies has inspirational mentalities and practices towards blood gift. Nonetheless, contributor enrollment projects and consistent blood gift battles are required to build the blood gift rate. **(Daştan et al., 2013)**

Blood gift rates are low in Turkey. Determination of the mentalities and practices of the nursing understudies who will work in wellbeing part and lead the general public with their insight and practices towards the blood gift is essential. The point of this study was to assess the relationship between the mentalities and practices of nursing understudies towards blood gift and their vehement propensities. Techniques: The study was directed 135 understudies in Kara Buk University Nursing Department between the October and November 2013. Information in this study was acquired by individual information shapes and the size of vehement inclination. Information were broken down with chi-square test, Spearman relationship investigation and autonomous examples t-test. The rate of blood gift among the members was low. In spite of the fact that the learning level of the nursing understudies was high, their insight in regards to the blood gift was lacking. The relationship amongst sexual orientation and blood gift is critical ($p=0.02$). There was no huge connection between the Empathic Tendency Scale

score of the members and their experience of blood gift ($p=0.83$). Social undertakings to energize the blood gifts ought to be produced and addresses that would add to the vehement propensities of the nursing understudies ought to be supported. **(Alok kumar, 2015)**

Blood transfusion is a therapeutic and life sparing system. In any case, Knowledge, state of mind, conviction and level of consciousness of blood transfusion may influence such technique. This present study was performed to decide the mentalities, convictions and information of patients towards blood transfusion in LadokeAkintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Oshogbo, Osun State. Five hundred (500) patients were haphazardly chosen and pre-test poll regulated. 18% had been transfused before while 82% had not been transfused. 80% of the respondents are prepared to acknowledge blood transfusion while 20% will deny blood transfusion. 86% can urge their relatives to acknowledge blood transfusion while 14% won't energize their relatives. Out of 500 members, 190(41.3%) have sufficient comprehension of blood transfusion. half of the respondents in this study would deny blood transfusion because of trepidation of diseases. Taking everything into account, the mentality of the respondents in this study is by and large attractive. In any case, information in regards to blood transfusion is inadequate, and the low preparation for blood transfusion is a reason for concern. Thusly, instructive projects on blood transfusion ought to be extended through different media, for example, the online networking (Facebook, Twitter and so on). This project ought to be utilized to spread blood transfusion does not posture critical wellbeing dangers. General society ought to likewise be educated that all quantifies are executed by Medical Laboratory Professionals working in the blood donation center to guarantee the gave blood is alright for beneficiaries. **(Alok kumar, 2015)**

This is an investigation of the learning mentality and routine of blood gift among students in Enugu State. The study was completed utilizing self-managed polls. 280 polls were disseminated, gathered and dissected. The study uncovered that 96.1% of the understudies found out about blood gift at one point or the other. It is additionally uncovered that 96.4% think about blood screening before gift. Notwithstanding this information, just 19.6% of our respondents have given blood before and 45.4% is for their relatives. Handling the issue of blood lack in our banks in this manner rests to a more prominent degree on unequivocally teaching the young people

on the significance of blood gift and clarifying their psyches of the apparent symptoms of blood gift since they contribute to a great extent to the greater part of contributors in the general public and 97.9% said they will give if taught fittingly. **(Alok kumar, 2015)**

Blood gift is critical for sparing individuals' lives as well as for the quest for a superior social and living environment, and willful blood gift is by a long shot the best. Point The point of the study was to recognize the socio demographic connects among blood benefactors all in all populace to comprehend the different components that can arrange the adjustment in the discernment and mindfulness about blood gift. Subjects and strategies This was a populace based cross-sectional study, led in the Blood Bank appended to a medicinal school in Bastar locale, Chhattisgarh, India, on 320 blood benefactors, chose subsequent to satisfying perfect contributor screening. By meeting strategy, utilizing the pre-tried organized close-finished poll, the information was gathered and broke down. Results-In our study we found that number blood gift was more among lesser taught individuals when contrasted with higher instructed individuals and the majority of the contributors had not known about blood parts. Conclusion-Most of the blood benefactors had not known about blood segments in our study. Blood gift was more among urban individuals contrasted with the rustic individuals. It may be a result of simple openness of the givers to the blood donation center. Shortcoming after blood gift is the most widely recognized because that have negative effect on intentional blood gift took after by trepidation about blood gift. Significant hotspot for inspiration among blood contributors was self-longing to help other people took after by Blood benefactor inspiration program. So broad usage of Voluntary blood giver inspiration programs in urban and additionally country range could be urgent in enhancing viability of benefactor enlistment and accomplish 100% intentional blood gift.**(Alok kumar, 2015)**

The recognitions toward deliberate blood gift could be impacted to a huge degree by socio-demographic variables of information among the all-inclusive community. A cross-sectional spellbinding study was done in two gatherings including 100 individuals every utilizing a self-regulated organized survey. One gathering contained patients and blood contributors from Attibele locale going to the healing center and blood donation center reason situated in a rustic suburb of Bangalore, while the other gathering was respondents from urban ranges of Bangalore. Majority of the respondents knew about the diverse ABO blood bunches (96%) and Rh sorts (92.

5%).The country populace had generally low mindfulness on blood transmissible illnesses (65%) when contrasted with urban respondents. (92%). In spite of the fact that a staggering 89% concur that blood gift is a respectable demonstration just 48% mean to give consistently. Routine of blood gift had male penchant and was higher among the individuals who were instructed past secondary school or more (56%).The most regular purposes behind not giving blood was no data in the matter of how to give blood (16%). Knowledge on blood transmissible maladies was low in rustic populace. Information on certain conditions when a qualified individual may give blood was low among the urban populace. Blood gift hone had male inclination and was more regular among those informed past secondary school. Blood gift practice was more regular among the urban subgroup. However, as the example size was little, advance studies are expected to comprehend the examples and different elements affecting blood gift in urban and rustic ranges.**(S. and B., 2015)**

The significant of blood supply relies on upon deliberate blood commitment. Blood transfusion plays a Vital part in therapeutic science and is in charge of sparing a huge number of lives the world over. The Study expected to recognize the components hindering and urging ability to give blood among blood Contributors. A cross-sectional study was executed and the reactions were gathered by connecting and talking about with the blood benefactor going to blood donation center. We utilized inductive substance investigation (ICA) for investigating the variables of blood gift. Thus, noteworthy crevice of 61.6% was distinguished between first time givers and rehash benefactors. In addition, the best inspiration component identified for blood gift was "free wellbeing registration" trailed by "money related Advantages". The negative variable which influences the blood gift were "awful gift experience", "mood of the blood donation center" trailed by "social issues". The study speaks to that blood bank need to give better post blood gift administrations furthermore need to sort out an awareness program for hindrance givers to empower them for rehash gift.**(S. and B., 2015)**

FDA is looking for exhortation from the board of trustees on the components of a composed proclamation of understanding for Entire Blood contributors, the need to build up least measures for clarifying the dangers and risks of blood gift, and the best methods accessible to present the announcement of comprehension to the blood contributor. This talk won't incorporate the issues of educated assent for examination in the blood gift setting.

The non-therapeutic staffs are included in extensive collaboration with the patients and their overseers, in some occasions more than doctors themselves. They are looked upon by the group as a wellspring of learning and inspiration for different wellbeing related matters. The impact of mentalities, standards and view of bolster staff on group inspiration different issues including blood gift is not broadly examined. To discover the recognition and perspectives of this gathering of doctor's facility staff about blood gift are likewise rare. A volunteer gathering of 23 non-restorative doctor's facility staffs were considered utilizing the 'Free posting' strategy. Of these 7 most expressive members were chosen for 'Heap Sorting' exercise. Information was investigated utilizing Visual Anthropic, adaptation 1.0 programming. Of 119 reactions recorded, 15 commonest reactions were utilized for heap sorting exercise. These then sorted into 5 groups in light of the impression of the respondents. The respondents could distinguish the areas with their perspective. Greater part of the respondents trusted that blood gift was generally considered as an honorable and life sparing act. It was watched that there were a few misinterpretations with respect to blood gift. The gathering likewise consented to these misguided judgments. Such activities help us to comprehend the diverse parts of a theme (blood gift) as saw by the objective gathering. Such a comprehension is essential to plan any training program for the gathering. Such studies help in giving the premise to more representative quantitative studies. **(Dhara and Dinesh, 2012)**

Examine and propose a hypothetical model that portrays blood giver choices to staff working in blood donation centers (medical attendants and others) in their endeavors to catch and hold givers. Investigation of a few studies on the inspirations to give blood in Spain over the most recent six years, and additionally past writing on the theme, the writers' encounters in the most recent 25 years in more than 15 Non Administrative Associations with various levels of obligations, their encounters as blood benefactors and the casual meetings created amid those 25 years. a model is proposed with various inside and outside elements that impact blood gift, and in addition the diverse phases of the basic leadership process. Conclusion: the information of the gift procedure allows the improvement of showcasing systems that build benefactors and gifts. **(Aldamiz-echevarria and Aguirre-Garcia., 2014)**

The present patterns of blood supply deficiency have raised the worry about the capacity to meet the blood item request later on. At the season of appeal for blood items particularly amid bubbly seasons, Malaysia can't experience the interest. Subsequently, the nature of human life is influenced. This has made the essential to comprehend the situation and perceiving the elements that may impact individuals' aim to give blood. The motivation behind this study based study is to research the ramifications of socio-demographic elements in measuring the goal of general society to include in a blood gift program particularly in Perlis populace, Malaysia. The discoveries showed that, among the socio-demographic elements, sexual orientation is anticipated to have the most prominent relationship with goal to give blood than others. Moreover, people who have blood gift involvement in life were more wanted to do again their conduct later on than the individuals who are definitely not. The new revelations created are accepted to be significant for future exploration and in addition in outlining future blood gift program so as to empower the interest of the general population. **(Hamid et al., 2013)**

There is a genuine jumble amongst interest and accessibility of blood in our nation. One of the imperative elements rousing individuals for giving blood is their association with staff of wellbeing offices counting bolster staff. The learning and view of bolster staff about blood gift have not been examined enough. Information was gathered from arbitrarily chose 100 healthcare bolster staff utilizing a pretested poll. The poll depended on earlier subjective examination of view of few of the potential members. 91% of the respondents felt that blood gift was not protected. Just 16% had satisfactory learning about qualification for blood gift and every one of them was females. 39% respondents had given blood themselves and 79% had family history of blood gift. None of the socio-demographic variables aside from youthful age were observed to be connected with better information or positive discernments about blood gift. Numerous among the individuals who had given blood additionally did not see blood gift as protected. Fear about blood being not legitimately utilized and not having been drawn nearer by anybody were commonest reasons for not giving. The information about security, qualification and inspiration for blood gift is exceptionally poor among the human services bolster staff. Endeavors must be made to teach these workers and advance intentional blood gift among them. Different motivators as recommended by workers themselves and a few worldwide bodies may be considered to

advance blood gift among social insurance bolster staff. **(Mullah, 2013)**

To survey the information, disposition and work on with respect to blood gift among the Saudi populace. In light of this study, a viable methodology can be made with respect to inspiration and enlistment of deliberate non-compensated blood contributors in future. This cross sectional study was done at the Military Doctor's facility, Sharourah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, amid January 2003. A sum of 500 grown-up guys was met. Every individual finished a poll in Arabic dialect containing epidemiological information and learning with respect to blood gift and reasons of blood gift or non-gift. Out of 500 people, 291 (58.2%) were contributors and 209 (41.8%) were non benefactors. Four hundred furthermore, seventy-one (94.2%) answered that a man more than 45-years old couldn't give blood. Fifty-one point two percent (107 out of 209) of the non-contributors replied that one can give blood once every year. Out of 291 benefactors, 186 (63.9%) gave blood for their relatives or companions and 105 (36.1%) were volunteer blood contributors. Eighty-nine non contributors (42.6%) answered that they were not drew closer by anyone' for blood gift and 80 (38.3%) viewed themselves as "unfit" for gift due to shortcoming. There are misguided judgments with respect to blood gift among the Saudi populace. This needs training and inspiration through spread of data with respect to blood gift especially on electronic media. **(Alam and Masalmeh, 2004)**

Blood gift is the main method for obtaining blood to meet crisis necessities in instances of street auto collisions, inconveniences of pregnancy and labor, different weak issue and surgical crises among others. All around, 80 million units of blood are given every year, except just two million units are given in sub-Saharan Africa where the need is colossal. The goal of this study was to decide the conduct of the understudies of a tertiary foundation in Nigeria towards deliberate blood gift. Materials and This is a distinct cross-sectional study, which included understudies of a tertiary foundation in Nigeria. A multistage inspecting method was utilized in selecting the members for this study. A semi-organized self-directed poll was utilized to gather data on socio-demographic attributes, information, state of mind and elements influencing willful blood gift. The information got were broke down utilizing EPI-Data 2005 programming Form 3.3.2. Fewer than 66% (61%) of aggregate respondents had great information of blood gift. More than seventy-five percent (85%) of the respondents had never given blood. Of the 15% that had given, just 3% gave

willfully. Among those that had ever given, guys (57%) were more than females. A considerable lot of the contributors gave for relatives (57%). Most of the respondents were constrained to give in light of crisis circumstances (75%). The reasons why numerous did not give were absence of chance (45%) because of tight address plan and lacking information (24%). Blessing things, for example, hematinic, Shirts and wrist groups (29%) would rouse respondents to give.

The Understudies' Union body and different Associations in the College ought to incorporate a blood gift drive in their month to month/yearly exercises. The College powers, the College wellbeing administration focus and the Hematology Branch of the Showing doctor's facility ought to team up in advancing intentional blood gift among the understudies. **(Salaudeen and Odeh, 2011)** With an expanding interest for blood and blood items in Australia, there is a nonstop need to enlist blood benefactors. In that capacity, it is essential to research the components that effect on non-benefactors' basic leadership forms with respect to giving blood for the main time. Previous research has set up the adequacy of the Hypothesis of Arranged Conduct (TPB) in foreseeing blood giver goals. The ebb and flow research planned to test a TPB model expanded with develops ensnared in past blood giver research; particularly expressive standard, moral standard, foreseen misgiving and gift uneasiness.

Members finished measures evaluating the standard TPB variables of demeanor, subjective standard, and saw behavioral control and also expressive standard, moral standard, gift uneasiness and expected misgiving. Way investigation analyzed the utility of the expanded TPB model to foresee 195 non-blood contributors' expectations to give blood. A last updated model gave a solid match to the information and included disposition, saw behavioral control, moral standard, distinct standard, foreseen misgiving and gift uneasiness as direct indicators of goal, with these elements representing 70% of the difference in intentions to give blood. Determination: A changed TPB model gave a more viable indicator of non-givers' expectations to give than the standard TPB model and highlights the part that standard based components and full of feeling loaded constructs play in foreseeing non-blood benefactors' expectations to give. **(Robinson et al., 2008)**

Sufficient and safe blood supply has remained a test in creating nations like our own. There is a high reliance on family substitution and compensated blood givers in our surroundings which conveys an orderly expanded danger of transfusion transmissible

infection. The destinations of this study were to evaluate the information, state of mind, and routine of deliberate blood gift among medicinal services laborers (non-physicians) and to distinguish and select potential willful blood benefactors. This was a cross-sectional distinct study did at the College of Benin Showing Healing center, Benin City. An aggregate of 163 staffs were selected. Pretest surveys were utilized to evaluate their insight, demeanor, and routine of willful blood donation. The reactions were ordered and dissected with the Measurable Bundle for Sociologies (SPSS) 16. The relationship between blood gift practice and sexual orientation of respondents, class of staff, and level of instruction was tried utilizing Chi-square and Fisher's tests where appropriate. $P < 0.05$ were considered factually significant. The middle time of the respondents was 32 years (18–56) with females representing 55.6% (90). An aggregate of 74.8% (122) accomplished tertiary instruction, and 55.8% (91) of respondents were senior staffs. The lion's share has great learning and inspirational state of mind towards gift; in any case, just 22.1% (36) have given blood with 41.7% (15) of these being intentional. Male specialists will probably give ($P < 0.05$). There is no critical relationship between blood gift and level of education. There is a solid uniqueness between the learning, disposition, and routine of intentional gift amongst human services specialists. (Nwogoh et al., 2013)

The adequacy of blood depends on blood donation rates and numbers of blood donors. To prepare adequate blood supplies, it is essential to investigate the barriers and factors that stop individuals from donating. This study aimed to identify the causes of lapsed donation at our center. We selected 850 donors who had donated between January 1, 2005 and June 1, 2005, but had not donated again by June 2008. The participants were recruited by letter and telephone, and were interviewed using a specially designed questionnaire that contained items on demographic characteristics, donor motivations and reasons for not returning to donate. We used the chi-square test to identify associations between lapsed donor characteristics and reasons for declining to donate. The greatest motivation for donation was altruism. The most frequent reasons for lapsed donation were lack of time because of work and self-exclusion for medical reasons. Among first-time donors, the most frequent reasons were unsuitability for donation and lack of time. The reasons for not returning to donate are varied and may correlate with demographic characteristics. In this study, the main reason for not returning was lack of time. Changing donation hours so that donors can donate after work,

providing mobile teams at workplaces, and shortening the duration of the donation process may help increase repeat donation rates. (Kasraian, 2010)

The absence of blood givers in the Assembled States is an issue. The reason for this study was to look at the relationship between blood gift learning and blood gift goals among understudies at Minnesota State College, Mankato (MNSU), also, analyze blood gift disposition and certainty levels among the respondents. A scientist developed electronic study was sent to 3, 944 MNSU understudies, with a total of 376 reactions ($n = 364$; balanced reaction rate = 9.23%). Examinations included unmistakable insights, autonomous specimen t-tests, recurrence numbers, and Pearson item minute connection coefficient tests. The mean aim scores of current blood givers were higher than non-blood contributors. The respondents' mean information score was respectably low (4.26), scoring just underneath the half check on the information appraisal. The part of respondents who had reported giving blood in the past was 56.5%. The blood gift states of mind among the respondents were reported as positive, with a mean attitudinal score of 6.48 out of 7. The certainty level of the respondents regarding feeling equipped for giving blood was reasonably high, with a mean score of 5.30 out of 7. A noteworthy relationship was distinguished between information and blood gift aims. A huge distinction amongst men and ladies and their blood gift information and dispositions was likewise distinguished. At long last, 60.6% of the respondents' wanted to get blood gift instructive materials through email administrations. (Allerson, 2012)

The interest for blood items in Australia is anticipated to increment significantly in coming years. However, populace development and population ageing will introduce challenges to blood benefactor enlistment and subsequently undermine the accessibility of satisfactory blood supplies for what's to come. Enhancing the maintenance of blood contributors offers a chance to influence this accessibility of blood items, and an emphasis on young fellows can be especially gainful in light of the fact that men turn into the greatest companion of givers later in life. This examination was led as a team with the Australian Red Cross Blood Administration. It connected a spellbinding phenomenological technique to investigate the elements that persuade young fellows to over and again give blood. Semi-organized meetings were directed to accumulate the motivational encounters of 11 youthful male blood contributors, and their stories were broken down as indicated by Colaizzi's (1978)

technique. The amplified hypothesis of arranged conduct (TPB) was connected as a hierarchical structure once the investigative procedure was finished. Nine topics developed as components of inspiration for the young fellows, each of which was subsumed by one of four hypothetical develops: demeanor, saw behavioral control [PBC], fulfillment, and self-character. Due to the way of the topics, it was finished up that the distinguished PBC and fulfillment constructs converged with the broadened TPB, what's more, that demeanor and self-character were more extensive than the hypothesis proposes. Proposals for future examination are given, and preparatory ramifications for mental hypothesis and Blood Administration rehearse are discussed. (Morris, 2011)

In spite of the fact that blood gift is a philanthropic conduct that people in general is when all is said in done exceptionally strong, the contributors must be always reminded for the gift needs on the grounds that blood has a constrained self-life and rehashed gift must be made after a restricted time interim. Different methodologies including television, radio, press, messages, contributor bulletin, site, open transportation safe houses and publication show in group have been used to pull in the givers to come back for blood gift. Taken a toll adequacy of these systems is rarely measured and behavioral study on benefactors and open is additionally rather constrained around there. Here we review the Chinese blood contributors on their state of mind towards the limited time systems received in Hong Kong. All qualified Chinese contributors matured fewer than 40 with a substantial email location are welcome to partake an online study in November 2008. They represented 77% of blood givers in Hong Kong. Benefactors were asked to rate on a 5-focuses pivot against the special procedures utilized by Hong Kong Red Cross Blood Transfusion Administration (BTS) and their apparent adequacy. 2,295 givers reacted to the welcome and finished the online review of whom 1,069 were matured somewhere around 16 and 25 and 1,226 somewhere around 26 and 40. The male to female proportion was 1.46: 1. All in all, most benefactors showed that the blood gift messages were gotten in the request of TV (score = 3.295), messages (3.09), blurbs at open transportation covers (2.71), radio (2.69), blurbs at group (2.63), benefactor bulletin (2.55), daily paper and magazine (2.54) and BTS site (2.39). They considered that TV and messages are the best in conveying limited time data. 30.8% givers respected the customary path of promotion of "offering gifts to the blood givers" and 21.4% liked to have famous people interest in the blood gift drive. Be that as it may, subgroup

investigation of the youthful era (matured 16-25) uncovered that "through the sharing gatherings on web" (score = 3.95) to be the most viable approach to advance blood gift. Ultimately a significant 16.4% and 13.3% considered the need of blood gift display and instructive sessions. (Hung et al., 2009)

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Contributor maintenance represents a critical issue to blood gathering offices around the globe. Past examination utilizing an increased Hypothesis of Arranged Conduct (TPB) approach has exhibited that disposition, subjective standard, self-adequacy, moral standard, foreseen lament, gift nervousness from earlier blood gifts and self-way of life as a blood contributor predicts encountered benefactors' goals and that expectations, self-adequacy, moral standard, what's more, foreseen misgiving may affect upon individuals' real blood gift conduct. Set up blood givers (N= 263) finished polls surveying standard TPB develops, foreseen lament, moral standard, gift nervousness, and self-way of life as a blood giver. Three months later, a second poll surveying blood gift conduct in the interceding three months was sent and returned by 182 givers. Utilizing basic equation modeling, the last enlarged TPB model gave an

amazing fit to the information and incorporated a direct path from aim to behavior and roundabout ways to conduct through goal for demeanor, self-adequacy and expected misgiving. Moral standard, gift uneasiness and giver personality by implication anticipated goal through demeanor. In complete, 51% of the difference in benefactors' states of mind, 86% of fluctuation in donors' aims, and 70% of the difference in givers' conduct was represented in the last model. An expanded TPB system demonstrated solid in deciding the indicators of the expectations and conduct of set up blood contributors. Further, this structure highlighted the significance of considering later on how contributors' inspirations for giving blood may advance as a component of the quantity of earlier gifts. **(Masser et al., 2009)**

Intentional non-compensated blood givers are viewed as the best among all distinctive sorts of blood contributors for enhancing the supply of safe blood. In spite of the fact that protected blood transfusion administrations have enhanced in Pakistan, yet endeavors are still required to advance blood donation centers and move forward enrollment of willful benefactors, for example, senior school/school going understudies as a wellspring of safe blood. This study investigates the consciousness of senior school youngsters concerning blood related issues counting blood gift. Strategies: This cross-sectional illustrative study selected 106 senior school understudies of non-public schools. Information were gathered through self - directed poll. Albeit 90% of the understudies considered blood as an essential element for sparing lives still 56.8% had never considered giving blood. Respondents had great information with respect to the conceivable spread of HIV/Helps, and Hepatitis B and C through dangerous transfusions. Conceivable obstacles to giving blood included trepidation of needles, apprehension of gaining infection, absence of learning as to give blood and absence of trust on bloodbanks. More than half of the understudies trusted that blood ought to be purchased from expert blood givers. Conclusions: Senior school going kids are not prepared to give blood. Absence of learning and winning confusions as to transfusions should be tended to and components to persuade and activate youth for getting to be willful blood contributors should be built up. **(Thaver et al., 2014)**

In the Unified States, blood item accessibility is reliant totally on gifts from volunteer blood givers. Current patterns in blood gathering and usage raise worries about the capacity to meet future requests for blood items. During a period of high interest and deferrals, the Furnished Administrations Blood Program has been not able meet its necessities for

blood and hence needs to buy blood from regular citizen offices to meet the double requests of the military group at home, and additionally those conveyed around the globe. This makes a need to better comprehend the military blood contributor in a push to enlist and hold those relative few who are willing and qualified to give. The motivation behind this study based examination is to portray the demographics of the military blood giver and to comprehend, through illustrative and relapse examination, the relationship between a giver's mentality, subjective standards, and saw behavioral control and their goal to give blood again in the following six months. The study employments the structure of the hypothesis of arranged conduct to plan the overview and assess connections between the hypothetical builds. Graphic investigation aftereffects of the example demographics depict the run of the mill respondent as White, youthful, male, and a lesser administration part. Aftereffects of the multivariate relapse examination demonstrated that a respondent's demeanor toward blood gift and saw behavioral control over giving blood were emphatically identified with their expectation to give again in the following six months. In any case, as opposed to the hypothesis, there was no measurably noteworthy relationship between the impact of subjective standards and goal to give once more. This study is the first to apply a hypothetical structure to recognize those elements that impact a military blood benefactor to give blood. Further, it has stepped to give an unmistakable depiction of the regular military blood benefactor. Future test examination can now be composed with the point of creating proficient and successful blood benefactor enlisting and maintenance crusades. In particular, the comprehension of the demographics of the populace permits focused on intercessions to underrepresented bunches, furthermore, hypothetical examination will facilitate guide intercessions that objective those vital motivational variables affecting blood gift. **(Kumari, 2014)**

Blood the liquid of life is RED paying little heed to the race or conviction or shading. The prepared accessibility of Blood of all sorts amid crisis can spare lives. Young people are a potential wellspring of extraordinary interest, not just for the blood they could supply, additionally on the grounds that data on the subject "giving blood" could advance the spread of solid ways of life, procurement of more noteworthy mindfulness about one's own particular wellbeing, and add to the improvement of a full grown, capable municipal disposition. This paper goes for not just finding motivational variables among blood benefactors and normal obstructions

they encounter while blood gift in spite of their extraordinary goal to give blood additionally in proposing the consolation procedures to advance new contributors among teenagers. A review on 300 youths obvious that their representations highlighted philanthropic viewpoints to the detriment of self-absorbed ones and self-insistence, yet appeared to be drawn more from the creative energy than from a genuine information of contributors. Strikingly, the understudies reported fearing needles or being unwell or blacking out after the blood gift process though just 16% of the understudies did not see any handy hindrance to give blood. The information concerning components encouraging gift affirm the thought that the understudies need straightforward, solid data, maybe acquired by going to perceive how a Transfusion Center functions, sometime recently choosing; a genuinely clear support appeared to be the likelihood of giving blood with somebody who has effectively done as such (42%). Understudies while chatting on the qualities of a decent limited time battle, the proposals were agreeable to two key components: an interesting message that is basic and clear; the various visual components assume an optional part. **(Kumari, 2014)**

Worldwide there is a shortage of dynamic blood benefactors, and the issue of pulling in and holding adequate benefactors to take care of demand for blood and blood items is a genuine one. This study has distinguished variables that disclose the choice to give blood. Therefore, the discoveries offer blood accumulation organizations direction with the assignment of detailing particular systems to address blood contributor deficiencies. Be that as it may, precisely foreseeing who is most liable to give blood stays risky, and further research is expected to amplify the discoveries reported in this study. **(Holdershaw et al., 2003)**

Like other created nations, just 3% of the aggregate populace in Hong Kong give blood (Hong Kong Red Cross Blood Transfusion Administration 2003). More than 20% of yearly gifts originate from adolescents matured 18-25. In any case, this class of givers has diminished steadily from 24.6% in 2004 to 22.9% in 2008. This study expects to analyze the qualities and expectation of youthful blood givers versus no donors in Hong Kong; and to investigate the components that may impact Hong Kong youngsters' gift conduct. This is a cross-sectional study utilizing survey to request data from youngsters including both blood benefactors and non-givers. It appeared that more non-givers were underweight (26%) than blood givers (16.9%). Blood benefactors showed to have more information on the use of gave blood (87.2%).

About portion of youth conceded that they made utilization of gift as methods for blood testing (53.1%) or free physical registration (47.3%). Recruitment techniques ought to concentrate on the improvement of wellbeing instruction programs identified with blood and blood gift for youngsters to expand their attention to blood and reduce their misguided judgments about blood gift. **(Hong and Loke, 2011)**

Safe blood is an essential part in enhancing medicinal services internationally and a large number of lives are spared every year through blood gift. Be that as it may, most healing centers in the creating nations face difficulties of steady supply of blood to do distinctive life sparing techniques that require blood, because of lack of blood contributors. Numerous studies have been done on the impression of blood gift however just a couple have been on Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Understudies. Point: To decide the view of blood gift among Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Understudies of NnamdiAzikiweCollege, Nnewi and Agulu Grounds separately. Stratified testing system was utilized to isolate the understudies into strata (200, 300, 400, 500, and 600), then straightforward irregular inspecting was utilized to choose distinctive respondents from every class and self-controlled surveys were given to the respondents. Information was gathered and results were examined. 294 respondents, 147 restorative understudies and 147 pharmaceutical understudies took an interest in the study 141 (95.9%) of restorative understudies and 137 (93.2%) of pharmaceutical understudies had known about blood gift. 139 (94.6%) of restorative understudies and 140 (95.2%) of pharmaceutical understudies knew their blood bunches. 59.5% of the respondents had given blood. The commonest inspiring component towards blood gift is "to spare a companion or relative". The learning of the understudies in regards to blood gift was high yet the act of blood gift was low. **(Nwabueze et al., 2014)**

Accessibility of blood for transfusion is of most extreme significance in the battle against maternal grimness and mortality. This study was led to distinguish the socio-demographic attributes and reasons of persons declining willful blood gift. Patients' relatives declining blood gift in rustic Ebonyi State were arbitrarily selected and met utilizing institutionalized poll in the wake of acquiring educated assent from each of them. Reactions were positioned concurring to recurrence of positive respondents. Lack of education was pervasive among the populace: more than 76% had no formal training. 'Not being sufficiently solid' and

'not having enough blood' were the two noteworthy explanations behind declining blood gift, while loss of masculinity/charisma and introduction of blood to witchcraft were alternate reasons given. Respondents' level of attention to HIV/Helps was obvious. Socio-social hindrances to deliberate blood gift exist in prevalently unskilled rustic groups of the nation. A large portion of the reasons given depended on misguided judgment, falsehood and lack of awareness about the impact and wellbeing of blood gift. (Umeora et al., 2005)

METHODOLOGY:

STUDY DESIGN: -

A cross-sectional survey was carried out to assess the people's perception regarding blood donation and awareness level of this activity including safe and harmful parameters.

STUDY POPULATION: -

The study population comprised of 350 people of general population of Bahawalpur.

STUDY SETTING: -

Study was conducted in city Bahawalpur of Southern Punjab.

SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Inclusion criteria: -

Only population of Bahawalpur City was included. Survey was carried out only on healthy individuals.

Exclusion criteria: -

Population outside Bahawalpur City was not included, even peripheral population was also not included.

Individuals suffering from fatal and life-threatening diseases were not included.

DATA COLLECTION:

Data Collection Tool:

A self-created questionnaire was used as a data collection tool. The questionnaire was consisting of questions which were used to analyze the people

perception regarding blood donation as well as its safe and harmful parameters. The questionnaire comprised of four major parts. Part one was designed to measure socio-demographic data for example age, gender, name of medical institute, class year and place of residence. Part two, three and four were about the knowledge, benefits and harms regarding blood donation.

Data Analysis procedure:

The data was entered and analyzed by using Statistical package for Social Science (SPSS version 21) for windows. Descriptive statistics was used to determine mean and standard deviation for continuous variables like age while frequency and percentage for quantitative variables. Scoring was done, for knowledge, each right response was given a score of 1 while a wrong or unsure response was scored 0.

Analysis Plan:

Descriptive statistics.

RESULT:

The response was gathered from a total of 350 respondents, the study sample consisted there were 219 males (62.6) and 131 females (37.4). Majority (85.42) were in age group of 18-25. The majority of participants (52.9%) were non donors among which (28%) were females. Among the donor group majority (37.71%) were males, 41.71% were educated up to graduation and intermediate, and among the non-donors 49.43% were also educated up to graduation and intermediate. Mostly 88.3% all the public were aware of blood donation. Among non-donors 52.9% never considered being a donor due to fear of needle (24%), harms of blood donation (fear of infection) (35.1%), mistrust and lack of information. Among the donor's major reason for donating blood was noble cause in 69.4%.

Table 1: Showed social demographic characteristic of the study participants. A total of 350 interviews were performed during data collection period. The mean age of participants was (23.45) years. Majority of respondents were males 219(62.6%), having age 18-25 years (52.85%), belonged to general population of Bahawalpur.

Characteristic	Frequency(percentage)	
Age	18	22(6.3)
	19	26(7.4)
	20	38(10.9)
	21	62(17.7)
	22	59(16.9)
	23	42(12.0)
	24	34(9.7)
	25	16(4.6)

	26	4(1.1)
	27	4(1.1)
	28	5(1.4)
	29	2(0.6)
	30	5(1.4)
	32	5(1.4)
	33	4(1.1)
	35	6(1.7)
	38	5(1.4)
	44	1(0.3)
	45	3(0.9)
	46	1(0.3)
	48	2(0.6)
	49	1(0.3)
	50	1(0.3)
	52	1(0.3)
	53	1(0.3)
Gender	Male	219(62.6)
	Female	131(37.4)
Marital status	Single	302(86.3)
	Married	47(13.4)
	Divorced	1(0.3)
	Widowed	0(0.0)
Number of Children	0	305(87.1)
	1-2	20(5.7)
	3-4	11(3.1)
	More than 5	14(4.0)
Education	Illiterate	10(2.9)
	Metric	21(6.0)
	Intermediate	44(12.6)
	Graduate	275(78.6)
Diseased Condition	Aids	1(0.3)
	Hepatitis	8(2.3)
	Any other disease	11(3.1)
	None	330(94.3)
Income	<5000	116(33.1)
	10,000-15,000	129(36.9)
	15,000-20,000	47(13.4)
	15,000-20,000	58(16.6)

TABLE 2: List of the perception of participant regarding blood donation.

Items	Frequency(percentage)	
Do you know the common blood groups?	Yes	309(88.3)
	No	41(11.7)
If yes, then what is your blood group?	A+	72(20.6)
	B+	110(31.4)
	AB+	38(10.9)
	A-	5(1.4)
	B-	15(4.3)
	O-	18(5.1)
	O+	68(19.4)
	AB-	4(1.1)

	Don't know	20(5.4)
Do you donate blood?	Yes	165(47.1)
	No	185(52.9)
If yes ,then you know how often can an individual donate?	Monthly	8(2.3)
	3 Month	92(26.3)
	6 Month	70(20.0)
	Annually	66(18.9)
	Don't know	114(32.6)
Do you know the benefits of blood donation?	Yes	207(59.1)
	No	78(22.3)
	Don't know	65(18.6)
Does blood donation improve blood count?	Yes	175(50.0)
	No	68(19.4)
	Don't know	107(30.6)
Does blood donation improve mental health?	Yes	147(42.0)
	No	82(23.4)
	Don't know	121(34.6)
Does blood donation reduce cancer risks?	Yes	119(34.0)
	No	92(26.3)
	Don't know	139(39.7)
Does blood donation reduce weight?	Yes	62(17.7)
	No	192(54.9)
	Don't know	96(27.4)
Does blood donation prevent the accumulation of toxic substances?	Yes	114(32.6)
	No	92(26.3)
	Don't know	144(41.4)
Does blood donation reduce the risk of heart diseases?	Yes	128(36.6)
	No	79(22.6)
	Don't know	143(40.9)
Is blood donation effective in reducing blood pressure and glucose level?	Yes	115(32.9)
	No	98(28.0)
	Don't know	137(39.1)
Do you know the harms of blood donation?	Yes	123(35.1)
	No	127(36.3)
Do you perform all required tests before donating blood?	Yes	180(51.4)
	No	170(48.6)
Does blood donation cause fatigue and dizziness?	Yes	168(48.0)
	No	81(23.1)
	Don't know	101(28.9)
Does blood donation cause heart disease problems?	Yes	47(13.4)
	No	172(49.1)
	Don't know	131(37.4)
Does blood donation cause injury to vein?	Yes	84(24.0)
	No	170(48.6)
	Don't know	96(27.4)
Do you think that it is safe for teenagers to donate blood?	Yes	145(41.4)
	No	123(35.1)

	Don't know	82(23.4)
Will you donate if called upon or reminded to donate blood?	Yes	214(61.1)
	No	134(38.3)
	Don't know	2(0.6)
Is blood donation a good practice?	Yes	243(69.4)
	No	58(16.6)
	Don't know	49(14.0)

TABLE 3: The p-value were applied and the significant correlation were observed between Gender and knowledge, Benefits and harms of perception of blood donation.

Dependent Variable		Gender		P-value or Fisher's exact
		MALE	FEMALE	
Do you know the common blood groups?	No	28(12.78)	13(9.92)	0.420
	YES	191(87.21)	118(90.07)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
If yes, then what is your blood group?	A+	45(20.5)	27(20.6)	<0.001
	B+	80(36.5)	30(22.9)	
	AB+	19(8.7)	19(14.5)	
	A-	2(0.9)	3(2.3)	
	B-	3(1.4)	12(9.2)	
	O-	8(3.7)	10(7.6)	
	O+	43(19.6)	25(19.1)	
	AB-	1(0.5)	3(2.3)	
	Don,t know	18(8.2)	2(1.5)	
TOTAL	219	131		
Do you donate blood?	No	87(39.7)	98(74.8)	<0.001
	YES	132(60.3)	33(25.2)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
If yes ,then you know how often can an individual donate?	Monthly	5(2.3)	3(2.3)	<0.001
	3 Month	82(37.4)	10(7.6)	
	6 Month	53(24.4)	17(13.0)	
	Annually	28(12.8)	38(29.0)	
	Don't know	51(23.3)	63(48.1)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Do you know the benefits of blood donation?	No	36(16.4)	42(32.1)	<0.001
	YES	152(69.4)	55(42.0)	
	Don't know	31(14.2)	34(26.0)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation improve blood count?	No	22(10.0)	46(35.1)	<0.001
	YES	138(63.0)	37(28.2)	
	Don't know	59(26.9)	48(36.6)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation improve mental health?	No	31(14.2)	51(38.9)	<0.001
	YES	113(51.6)	34(26.0)	
	Don't know	75(34.2)	46(35.1)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation reduce cancer risks?	NO	37(16.9)	55(42.0)	<0.001
	YES	95(43.4)	24(18.3)	
	Don't know	87(39.7)	52(39.7)	

	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation reduce weight?	NO	122(55.7)	70(53.4)	0.60
	YES	45(20.5)	17(13.0)	
	Don't know	52(23.7)	44(33.6)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation prevent the accumulation of toxic substances?	NO	44(20.1)	48(36.6)	0.001
	YES	83(37.9)	31(23.7)	
	Don't know	92(42.0)	52(39.7)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation reduce the risk of heart diseases?	No	36(16.4)	43(32.8)	<0.001
	YES	100(45.7)	28(21.4)	
	Don't know	83(37.9)	60(45.8)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Is blood donation effective in reducing blood pressure and glucose level?	NO	48(21.9)	50(38.2)	0.001
	YES	86(39.3)	29(22.1)	
	Don't know	85(38.8)	52(39.7)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Do you know the harms of blood donation?	No	81(37.0)	46(35.1)	0.896
	YES	75(34.2)	48(36.6)	
	Don't know	63(28.8)	37(28.2)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Do you perform all required tests before donating blood?	No	83(37.9)	87(66.4)	<0.001
	YES	136(62.1)	44(33.6)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation cause fatigue and dizziness?	No	60(27.4)	21(16.0)	0.048
	YES	98(44.7)	70(53.4)	
	Don't know	61(27.9)	40(30.5)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation cause heart disease problems?	NO	120(54.8)	52(39.7)	0.002
	YES	20(9.1)	27(20.6)	
	Don't know	79(36.1)	52(39.7)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Does blood donation cause injury to vein?	No	124(56.6)	46(35.1)	<0.001
	YES	42(19.2)	42(32.1)	
	Don't know	53(24.2)	43(32.8)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Do you think that it is safe for teenagers to donate blood?	NO	69(21.5)	54(41.2)	0.121
	YES	99(42.2)	46(35.1)	
	Don't know	51(23.3)	31(23.7)	
	TOTAL	219	131	
Will you donate if called upon or reminded to donate	No	63(28.8)	71(54.2)	<0.001
	YES	155(70.8)	59(45.0)	
	Don't know	1(0.5)	1(0.8)	

blood?	TOTAL	219	131	
Is blood donation a good practice?	NO	20(9.1)	38(29.0)	<0.001
	YES	168(76.7)	75(57.3)	
	Don't know	31(14.2)	18(13.7)	
	TOTAL	219	131	

DISCUSSION:

Keeping up a satisfactory and safe blood supply is principle issue of worry to neighborhood wellbeing organizers particularly with the expansion sought after as a consequence of an increment in populace size and an expansion in the quantity of medicinal offices in Pakistan. In this study contributors will probably be male (62.6%) than females (37.4%). (Agbovi et al., 2006)

Most studies led in Africa reports a male strength in blood gift programs (61% in Togo), (71.2% in Burkina Faso) and (90% in Ghana). (Allain et al., 2008). In an overview in Central, Western, and Eastern African districts, every one of these nations reviewed reported under 30% females in their benefactor populace. (Tagny et al., 2009). Reports from Anglophone East and Southern African nations have likewise demonstrated a male predominance in their blood gift programs. (Cunha et al., 2007)

In 2003 female blood benefactors spoke to 40% of the blood contributor populace in Austria, 49.7% in France, half in Norway and 55% in Great Britain. (Lefrère and Rouger, 2011). Essentially, Greece and Italy appears the main European nations in which the rate of female contributors is around 33%. (Bani and Giussani, 2010). In Spain, 46% of the blood contributors are ladies, (de Sangre) in Portugal 43%, (Bani and Giussani, 2010) in Belgium 45.4%, (Seifried et al., 2011) in the Netherlands half, (Wiggers et al., 1991) in France half, (Erhabor et al., 2014) and in Finland 55%. (Reesink et al., 2012).

The purpose behind this male sexual orientation power in the blood gift process in Pakistan might be founded on various elements which incorporate convictions that annoys on religion and culture and difficulties connected with giver instruction. A past report in Saudi Arabia an Islamic country showed that around 91% of the benefactors trusted that blood gift is a religious obligation (Gader et al., 2011).

This high rate of Islamic religion-related obligation to blood gift may, to some degree, be founded on the religious decision ["fatwa"] from the most regarded

religious priest, the late Sheik Abdul Aziz Bin Baz, who instructed that it is the obligation with respect to a Muslim to give blood to spare the life of a penniless patient. Leaflets conveying his "fatwa" are put in most contributor focuses in Saudi Arabia. Instruction is additionally an imperative element for giving blood. Most of the time individuals believe that by giving blood we may get some risky sickness like AIDS and Hepatitis. In Pakistan more often than not the general population having low pay give blood more than one having high income. In Pakistan connection is additionally an imperative variable which impact blood gift. obviously we give blood to a man more effortlessly which is in our connection than a man which is obscure for us. Profound quality is additionally a critical thing that a man with high good values effectively give blood than other. Confusion about blood gift is additionally a typical thing, individuals feel that by giving blood they may inclined to weight or might be stout. Alternately some time inclined to consanguineous infection. More often than not individuals don't urge or requested that give blood. They don't think this is a decent deed. Thomson et al reported that each year 80% of first time givers universally could stay away for the indefinite future to give (Thomson et al., 1998)

Rajagopalan et al reported that contributors and non-givers in therapeutically situated populace including medicinal and nursing understudies don't contrast essentially in their conclusion towards blood gift however need inspiration (Rajagopalan and Pulimood, 1998). It has been accounted for that age, race and sexual orientation are imperative identifiers of those less eager to give (Boulware et al., 2002).

Munoz et al reported that French populace has confusion with respect to gaining AIDS and hepatitis C disease as a consequence of donation. Subsequently, diminishing the discernment that the blood gift is not unsafe can prompt an expansion in blood gift. There were likewise purposes behind not giving blood, for example, "apprehensive of needles", "not intrigued and "absence of data. (Sastre et al., 2002).

CONCLUSION:

The study conducted in Bahawalpur City and its peripheries. The study shows that most of the people had false perception about blood donation. Most of them think that they may suffer from disease. A big number of females do not donate blood due to not having the reasonable and adequate information about blood donation. Most people donate blood think that it is a noble cause. The knowledge about blood donation should be delivered properly in Hospitals, Colleges, Universities so that significant number of people donate blood to rescue the patients. Now a days Seminars can be conducted to explain people misperception about blood donation. A campaign should be conducted under blood donation center's which can elaborate people about the benefits of blood donation. Medical profession students should also participate in the campaign. Education play a key role in blood donation. Mostly blood is donated by educated person. Non educated person only confine to their relation to donate blood.

Recommendations:

It is imperative to teach the importance of blood donation early in medical school. Seminars should be conducted relating blood donation that can sort out people false perceptions. Social, current and print media should be use to educate people about blood donation. Government should make plans to increase the literacy rate which can help people to understand the benefits of blood donation.

REFERENCES:

1. AGBOVI, K., KOLOU, M., FÉTÉKÉ, L., HAUDRECHY, D., NORTH, M. & SÉGBÉNA, A. 2006. [Knowledge, attitudes and practices about blood donation. A sociological study among the population of Lome in Togo]. *Transfusion clinique et biologique: journal de la Societe francaise de transfusion sanguine*, 13, 260-265.
2. AHMED, Z., ZAFAR, M., KHAN, A. A., ANJUM, M. U. & SIDDIQUE, M. A. 2014. Knowledge, attitude and practices about blood donation among undergraduate medical students in Karachi. *Journal of Infectious Diseases and Therapy*, 2014.
3. AL-DREES, A. M. 2008. Attitude, belief and knowledge about blood donation and transfusion in Saudi population. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 24, 74.
4. AL-FARIS, A. K., BAHABRI, A. S., AL-AQEEL, A. A. & AL-MOMI, M. S. 2013. Attitude to blood donation among male students at King Saud University. *Journal of Applied Hematology*, 4, 70.
5. AL-RAHILI, N. H., AL-JOHANI, W. A., AL-MUTAIRI, M. A., AL-REHAILI, S. H., AL-SUHAYMI, I. A. & AL-NAZZAWI, A.-A. O. 2015. Knowledge and Intentions toward Blood Donation among Medical Students of Taibah University, Madinah, Saudi Arabia 2015. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 4.
6. ALAM, M. & MASALMEH, D. B. D. 2004. Knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding blood donation among the Saudi population. *Saudi medical journal*, 25, 318-321.
7. ALDAMIZ-ECHEVARRIA, C. & AGUIRRE-GARCIA, M. S. A behavior model for blood donors and marketing strategies to retain and attract them., 2014.
8. ALLAIN, J. P., SARKODIE, F., BOATENG, P., ASENSO, K., KYEREMATENG, E. & OWUSU-OFORI, S. 2008. A pool of repeat blood donors can be generated with little expense to the blood center in sub-Saharan Africa. *Transfusion*, 48, 735-741.
10. ALLERSON, J. 2012. Assessment of Selected University Students' Knowledge of Blood Donation and the Relationship with Intent to Donate Blood.
11. ALOK KUMAR, A. M. B. R., NITIN GANGANE & V. JYOTI 2015. Socio-Demographic Profiles of Blood Donors in Bastar Region, Chhattisgarh: A Prospective Study. *International Journal of Current Medical And Applied Sciences*, 7, 3.
13. BAĞIŞI, K. & SONUÇLARI, A. 2012. Blood donation: survey results. *Age (years)*, 18, 760.
14. BANI, M. & GIUSSANI, B. 2010. Gender differences in giving blood: a review of the literature. *Blood Transfus*, 8, 278-287.
15. BATIHA, A.-M. & ALBASHTAWY, M. 2016. Attitudes and practices of health science students regarding blood donation. *International Journal of Advanced Nursing Studies*, 5, 81.
16. BOULWARE, L., RATNER, L. E., COOPER, L. A., SOSA, J. A., LAVEIST, T. A. & POWE, N. R. 2002. Understanding disparities in donor behavior: race and gender differences in willingness to donate blood and cadaveric organs. *Medical care*.
17. CUNHA, L., PLOUZEAU, C., INGRAND, P., GUDO, J. P. S., INGRAND, I., MONDLANE, J., BEAUCHANT, M. & AGIUS, G. 2007. Use of replacement blood donors to study the epidemiology of major blood-borne viruses in

- the general population of Maputo, Mozambique. *Journal of medical virology*, 79, 1832-1840.
18. DAŞTAN, N. B., DAŞTAN, M. & KIRANŞAL, N. 2013. Practices and attitudes towards blood donation in health high school students. *International Journal of Human Sciences*, 10, 293-306.
 19. DE SANGRE, F. E. D. D. Datos estadísticos de la donacion de sangre en Espana [Internet]. 2013 [acceso 4 jun 2013].
 20. DHARA, A. & DINESH, K. 2012. A Qualitative Study Of Perceptions About Voluntary Blood Donation Among The Supportive Service Employees Of A Multispeciality Rural Tertiary Care Hospital.
 21. ERHABOR, O., ISAAC, Z., ABDULRAHAMAN, Y., NDAKOTSU, M., IKHUENBOR, D., AGHEDO, F., IBRAHIM, K. & IBRAHIM, S. 2014. Female gender participation in the blood donation process in resource poor settings: case study of Sokoto in North Western Nigeria. *Journal of Blood Disorders & Transfusion*, 2014.
 22. GADER, A. G. M. A., OSMAN, A. M. A., AL GAHTANI, F. H., FARGHALI, M. N., RAMADAN, A. H. & AL-MOMEN, A. K. M. 2011. Attitude to blood donation in Saudi Arabia. *Asian journal of transfusion science*, 5, 121.
 23. HAMID, N. Z. A., BASIRUDDIN, R. & HASSAN, N. 2013. The intention to donate blood: an analysis of socio-demographic determinants. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 3, 503.
 24. HAOSSES-GORASES, L. & KATJIRE, M. 2013. Assessment of Knowledge, Beliefs, Perceptions Attitudes and Practices on Voluntary Non-remunerated Blood Donations in Namibia. *Online Journal of Medicine and Medical Science Research*, 2, 72-81.
 25. HOLDERSHAW, J., GENDALL, P. & WRIGHT, M. 2003. Factors influencing blood donation behaviour. University of Otago.
 26. HONG, J. & LOKE, A. Y. 2011. Hong Kong young people's blood donation behavior. *Asian journal of transfusion science*, 5, 49.
 27. HUNG, A., CHAU, M. & LEE, C. Chinese Perception of Blood Donation Promotional Strategies. *TRANSFUSION*, 2009. WILEY-BLACKWELL PUBLISHING, INC COMMERCE PLACE, 350 MAIN ST, MALDEN 02148, MA USA, 246A-246A.
 28. KASRAIAN, L. 2010. Causes of discontinuity of blood donation among donors in Shiraz, Iran: cross-sectional study. *Sao Paulo Medical Journal*, 128, 272-275.
 29. KUMARI, D. P. L. 2014. Blood donation among Adolescents -
 30. Motivation, Obstacles and Encouragement
 31. Strategies. *IJSR - INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH*, 3.
 32. LEFRÈRE, J.-J. & ROUGER, P. 2011. *Pratique nouvelle de la transfusion sanguine*, Elsevier Masson.
 33. MAMATYA, A., PRAJAPATI, R. & YADAV, R. 2012. Knowledge and practice of blood donation: a comparison between medical and non-medical Nepalese students. *Nepal Med Coll J*, 14, 283-286.
 34. MASSER, B. M., WHITE, K. M., HYDE, M. K., TERRY, D. J. & ROBINSON, N. G. 2009. Predicting blood donation intentions and behavior among Australian blood donors: testing an extended theory of planned behavior model. *Transfusion*, 49, 320-329.
 35. MIRZA, H., KHAN, F. & NAEEM, F. J. Blood Safety and Donation Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) among 1st Year Medical Students at LMDC, Lahore.
 36. MORRIS, A. 2011. Blood donor motivation: a phenomenological study of young male donors.
 37. MULLAH, F. 2013. Study of knowledge, perceptions and practices related to blood donation among the healthcare support staff of a tertiary care hospital in Gujarat, India. *Online Journal of Health and Allied Sciences*, 12.
 38. NWABUEZE, S., NNEBUE, C., AZUIKE, E., EZENYEAKU, C., ANIAGBOSO, C., EZEMONYE, O. & AZUIKE, E. 2014. Perception of Blood Donation among Medical and Pharmaceutical Science Students of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. *Open Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 2014.
 39. NWOGO, B., AIGBERADION, U. & NWANNADI, A. I. 2013. Knowledge, attitude, and practice of voluntary blood donation among healthcare workers at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, Benin City, Nigeria. *Journal of blood transfusion*, 2013.
 40. PRANJALI P. SHARMA, D. S. K., DR. AARTI KINIKAR DR. VISHAL, DR. VISHAL PATIL 2013. A Study of the Knowledge, Attitude and Practices
 41. Regarding Blood Donation in the Relatives of
 42. Paediatric Patients in a Tertiary Care Centre. *INDIAN JOURNAL OF APPLIED RESEARCH*, 3.
 43. RAJAGOPALAN, M. & PULIMOOD, R. 1998. Attitudes of medical and nursing students towards blood donation. *National Medical Journal of India*, 11.

44. REESINK, H., LEE, J., KELLER, A., DENNINGTON, P., PINK, J., HOLDSWORTH, R., SCHENNACH, H., GOLDMAN, M., PETRASZKO, T. & SUN, J. 2012. Measures to prevent transfusion-related acute lung injury (TRALI). *Vox sanguinis*, 103, 231-259.
45. ROBINSON, N. G., MASSER, B. M., WHITE, K. M., HYDE, M. K. & TERRY, D. J. 2008. Predicting intentions to donate blood among nondonors in Australia: an extended theory of planned behavior. *Transfusion*, 48, 2559-2567.
46. S., S. & B., C. 2015. STUDY ON IDENTIFICATION OF THE FACTORS IMPACTING BLOOD DONATION IN JHARKHAND, INDIA. *Indian Journal of Fundamental and Applied Life Sciences* ISSN, 5.
47. SALAUDEEN, A. & ODEH, E. 2011. Knowledge and behavior towards voluntary blood donation among students of a tertiary institution in Nigeria. *Nigerian journal of clinical practice*, 14, 303-307.
48. SASTRE, M. A. T. M., BACQ, Y., MULLET, E. & SORUM, P. C. 2002. Misconceptions regarding hepatitis C in the French public. *Preventive medicine*, 34, 596-599.
49. SEIFRIED, E., KLUETER, H., WEIDMANN, C., STAUDENMAIER, T., SCHREZENMEIER, H., HENSCHLER, R., GREINACHER, A. & MUELLER, M. 2011. How much blood is needed? *Vox sanguinis*, 100, 10-21.
50. SREEDHAR KRISHNA 2008. How did blood transfusion in Britain work during WWII and its significance. *Journal of Archeology, History and Anthropology*, 2.
51. TAGNY, C. T., DIARRA, A., YAHAYA, R., HAKIZIMANA, M., NGUESSAN, A., MBENSA, G., NÉBIÉ, Y., DAHOUROU, H., MBANYA, D. & SHIBOSKI, C. 2009. Characteristics of blood donors and donated blood in sub-Saharan Francophone Africa. *Transfusion*, 49, 1592-1599.
52. THAVER, D. H., MASUD, N. & ASHRAF, M. 2014. Are school children ready to donate blood? *Journal of Ayub Medical College, Abbottabad: JAMC*, 26, 68.
53. THOMSON, R., BETHEL, J., LO, A., OWNBY, H., NASS, C. & WILLIAMS, A. 1998. Retention of "safe" blood donors. The retrovirus epidemiology donor study. *Transfusion*, 38, 359-367.
54. TO, M. A. W. I. C. 2011. By Kristine Weiss Adams, MSN, CNP, and Deborah Tolich, MSN, RN.
55. UMEORA, O., ONUH, S. & UMEORA, M. 2005. Socio-cultural barriers to voluntary blood donation for obstetric use in a rural Nigerian village. *African journal of reproductive health*, 72-76.
56. WIGGERS, P., DALHØJ, J., KIAER, H., RING-LARSEN, H., PETERSEN, P. H., BLAABJERG, O. & HØRDER, M. 1991. Screening for haemochromatosis: prevalence among Danish blood donors. *Journal of internal medicine*, 230, 265-270.
57. WINDLEY, J. O. 2006. Young Blood: Persuading young people to give blood by applying concepts of self-perception and social norms theories to recruitment ads. *Citeseer*.